

EVALUATION OF SYNERGISTIC EFFECTS OF POLYHERBAL FORMULATIONS AND DOXORUBICIN IN DMBA INDUCED BREAST CANCER IN RATS

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 23/01/2021

Available online

01/03/2021

Keywords

Breast Cancer,
Doxorubicin,
Polyherbal Formulations.

ABSTRACT

Background: Breast cancer is the most common invasive cancer in women, and the second main cause of cancer death in women, after lung cancer. Traditional medicine has been used to treat various types of cancer and these are found to be effective with minimal or no side effects. Objective: To evaluate the anticancer activity of polyherbal formulations (PGM-12 and PGM-13), Doxorubicin and combination of both in DMBA induced breast cancer in rats. Methodology: The mammary gland tumor in rats was induced by a single dose of 65mg/kg p.o of DMBA. After development of visible tumors, the rats were administered with polyherbal formulations (200mg/kg/p.o/day of PGM-12 and PGM-13), Doxorubicin (2.5mg/kg/i.p/ week) and combination of both polyherbal formulations and Doxorubicin for a period of 8 weeks. The anticancer activity of the polyherbal formulation was assessed by recording difference in tumor volume, tumor weight and histopathological examination of tumors after the study. To evaluate nephroprotective effect of treatment renal functional parameters and renal antioxidant enzymes were also measured. Results: The treatment with polyherbal formulations, Doxorubicin and combination showed a significant decrease in the tumor size and tumor weight compared to positive control. The polyherbal formulations has improved the renal function parameters and increased the antioxidant enzymes level significantly compared to positive control and doxorubicin group. Conclusion The findings of our study revealed that the combination of polyherbal formulation and doxorubicin exerted synergistic effect by inhibiting the tumor growth. The combination protected the kidney from the nephrotoxic effect of Doxorubicin in DMBA-induced mammary tumor in rats.

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Please cite this article in press as **Roohith et al.** Evaluation of Synergistic Effects of Polyherbal Formulations and Doxorubicin DMBA Induced Breast Cancer in Rats. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2021;11(02).

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INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is a malignant tumor that starts in the cells of the breast. It is a heterogeneous disease with a variety of pathological entities and diverse clinical behavior growth. ^[1] More than 70% of death in developing countries occurred due to cancer, amongst all cancers, breast cancer is one of main types of cancer in world. In the year 2001, nearly 0.80 million new cancer cases of breast cancer were estimated in India and this has increased to 1.22 million by 2016. ^[2]

The main cause of breast cancer is Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH) which is commonly found in our environment, and they can be isolated from diesel exhaust, barbequed meat, tobacco smoke, overheated cooking oil, etc (4). PAH are metabolized and remodeled into DNA attacking electrophiles in the body leading to formation of PAH –DNA adducts in human breast tumors. ^[3] Breast cancer and cancer related diseases are treated using surgery, chemotherapy and radiation therapy which are usually associated with adverse effects and high cost. ^[4]

Amongst the chemotherapeutic options available, Doxorubicin (DOX)-based regimens, are preferred due to its high antitumor efficacy. ^[5] However, its use is limited due to severe (dose-dependent) side effects on healthy tissues such as heart, liver and kidney. Furthermore it can lead to drug resistance in breast cancer cells, which is another cause of its failure. ^[6]

Because of these several short comings of chemotherapy, there is a need in cancer research towards traditionally used herbal drugs which are devoid of these side effects and can be used with Doxorubicin to reduce the adverse effects associated with it.

The synthetic Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), 7, 12-dimethylbenz (a) anthracene (DMBA) initiates the production of free radicals that induce carcinogenesis in rats which imitate human breast cancers morphologically and histologically. ^[7] Therefore we used DMBA induced mammary gland carcinogenesis model in experimental animals.

The polyherbal formulation PGM 12 contains herbs such as Curcuma longa, Piper longum, Aspholtumpunjabinume, Vitis vinifera, Swertiachirata, Withaniasomenifera, Ocimumsantum and Zingiberofficinale.

The polyherbal formulation PGM 13 consists of herbal extracts such as Phycocyanin, Astaxanthin, Lycopene, Green Tea Extract, Resveratrol, Silymarin, Piperine, Andrographolide and Ginger. The herbs and herbal extracts used in this formulations are proven to possess anticancer and antioxidant potential individually. So the objective of this study is to evaluate the synergistic effects of polyherbal formulations and Doxorubicin in DMBA induced breast cancer in rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

Chemicals:

DMBA (7, 12 dimethyl Benz-anthracene) was purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry. Doxorubicin was from himedia. Herbal formulations (PGM12 and PGM13) are provided by NeocyteHerbtech, Bangalore. Other chemicals used in study were of analytical grade.

Animals:

50 days old female Wistar albino rats weighing 140-160g were obtained from central animal house of institute. They were maintained under standard environmental conditions and provided with fresh food and water *ad libitum*. The experimental protocol was approved by Institutional Animal Ethical Committee of Al-Ameen College Of Pharmacy (Approval No: AACP/IAEC/Jan2016/04). The handling of animals and experimental procedure followed the guidelines of Committee for the Purpose of control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA). The cancerous animals were daily monitored for any signs of pain and distress.

Induction of Cancer:

Breast cancer in female Wistar rats was induced at the age of 40- 50 days by administering a single dose of chemical DMBA (7, 12-dimethylbenz[a]anthracene) (65 mg/kg b.w.) in sesame oil to the rats by oral route of administration ^[8]

Treatment regimen:

After 90 days of induction period animals with the development of visible tumors were included in study and divided into following groups. Each group consists 11 animals except normal group with 6 animals

Group 1: Normal control.

Group 2: DMBA control

Group 3: DMBA+ Doxorubicin (2.5mg/kg b.w/i.p/weekly once).

Group 4: DMBA+ Doxorubicin (2.5mg/kg b.w/i.p/weekly once) + Polyherbal formulations (200mg/kg b.w/p.o/daily).

Group 5: DMBA+ Polyherbal formulations (200mg/kg b.w/p.o/daily).

General health parameters:

Effect of drugs on body weight and food and water intake:

The weight of animals were recorded every alternate week of study period, the food and water intake was monitored everyday on a 12 hour cycle.

Tumor parameters:**Effect of drugs on tumor volume:**

Tumor size was measured by using Vernier calipers & recorded in centimeters. Tumor volume was calculated by using the formula,

$$\text{Tumor volume: } \pi/6 (a^2) (b)$$

Where, a- Smallest length of the tumor.

b- Longest length of the tumor.

Effect of drugs on tumor weight:

At the end of treatment, tumors were excised and weighed and difference in weight of tumor was recorded.

Biochemical parameters:

After 60 days of treatment female rats were mildly anaesthetized as per CPCSEA guidelines and blood sample from each rats was collected in heparinized vials. Blood was centrifuged at 2300 r.p.m. for 15 minutes. Supernatant was used for biochemical analysis.

Serum Creatinine, Blood Urea Nitrogen and Serum Albumin were estimated using semi-auto analyzer and commercially available kits from Agappe (Agappe diagnostic Ltd.)

Renal oxidative stress parameters:

The animals were sacrificed and kidney and tumors were isolated. Right kidney was washed with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) to remove blood cells. Kidney was homogenized in cold phosphate buffer and the homogenates were centrifuged for 2min at 10,000rpm. The supernatant of tissue homogenate was used for the estimation of CAT (method of Aebi⁹), SOD (method of Beauchamp and Fridovich¹⁰) and GSH(method of Draper and Hadley¹¹).

Histopathology of tumors and kidney:

The isolated organs were stored in 10% formalin solution. H and E staining was performed and effect of treatment on tumor architecture and kidney architecture was evaluated.

STATISTICS:

Values are presented as mean±standard error of mean. One-way ANOVA analysis of variance followed by Tukey's multiple comparison tests was employed to evaluate statistical significance. Statistical calculations were performed using GraphPad Prism version 5 (GraphPad software company, La Jolla, CA, USA). P value <0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS**General health parameters:****Effect of treatment on body weight:**

There was a significant decrease in the body weight of animals administered with DMBA and treated with Doxorubicin when compared to negative control. Decrease in body observed with Doxorubicin was attenuated when administered in combination with polyherbal formulations. Group treated with polyherbal formulations showed significant increase in body weight. (Fig 1)

Fig 1: Effect of treatment on % Change in body weight.

Effect of treatment on food intake:

There was a significant decrease in the food intake of animals administered with DMBA and treated with Doxorubicin when compared to negative control. Decrease in food intake observed with Doxorubicin was attenuated when administered in combination with polyherbal formulations. Group treated with polyherbal formulations showed significant increase in food intake. (Fig 2)

Fig 2 : Effect of treatment on % Food intake.

Tumor parameters:**Effect of treatment on tumor weight:**

There was a significant decrease in the tumor weight of animals treated with doxorubicin and polyherbal formulations compared to animals administered with DMBA control. There was a further decrease in tumor weight observed when doxorubicin was co-administered along with polyherbal formulations. (Fig-3)

Fig 3: Effect of treatment on tumor weight.

Effect of treatment on tumor volume:

There was a significant decrease in the tumor volume of animals treated with doxorubicin and polyherbal formulations compared to animals administered with DMBA(positive control). There was a further decrease in tumor weight observed when doxorubicin was co-administered along with polyherbal formulations. (Fig-4)

Fig 4: Effect of treatment on tumor volume.

Expressed as mean±SEM; n=6 **($P<0.01$), ***($P<0.001$) when compared with DMBA administered rats by using one way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test. Doxo= Doxorubicin, PHF's = Polyherbal Formulaions.

Biochemical parameters:

Effect of treatment on biochemical parameters:

There was a significant increase in serum creatinine, blood urea nitrogen and serum albumin observed in animals administered with DMBA and treated with Doxorubicin which is indicative of nephrotoxicity associated with it, but there was a significant reduction in serum creatinine, blood urea nitrogen and serum albumin values of animals treated with combination therapy and polyherbal formulations had biochemical parameters values significantly lower when compared to animals administered with DMBA and animals treated with Doxorubicin. (Table No-1)

Table No-1: Effect of treatment on biochemical parameters and renal oxidative stress parameters.

Groups	PARAMETERS					
	Serum Creatinine	Blood Urea Nitrogen	Serum Albumin	SOD(Kidney)	Catalase (Kidney)	GSH (Kidney)
NC	0.32±0.047	17.13±0.76	2.65± 0.19	119.1± 3.70	74.03± 1.32	24.30± 0.75
DMBA	0.73± 0.018	26.02±0.49	4.09± 0.23	63.01± 2.786	35.06± 1.17	13.01± 0.65
DMBA+Doxo	0.901± 0.047	28.12± 0.4	4.35± 0.179	52.48± 3.75	45.90± 1.74	10.29± 0.44
DMBA+Doxo+PHF's	0.525±0.039	21.38± 0.70	2.97± 0.20	84.47± 3.523	55.27± 1.902	18.75± 0.23
DMBA+PHF's	0.39± 0.029	19.38± 0.49	2.79± 0.12	110.4± 2.026	67.18± 1.731	21.62± 0.71

Renal oxidative stress parameters:

Effect of treatment on SOD, CAT and GSH in kidney homogenate:

There was a significant decrease SOD, CAT and GSH in observed in animals treated with Doxorubicin which is indicative of nephrotoxicity and oxidative stress associated with it, but the SOD, CAT and GSH values of animals treated with polyherbal formulations in combination of Doxorubicin and polyherbal formulations had SOD, CAT and GSH values significantly higher when compared to animals administered with DMBA and animals treated with Doxorubicin. (Table No-1)

Histopathological examination of kidney and tumor.

Effect of treatment on kidney pathology:

The histopathological examination of kidney tissue of normal rats showed the normal appearance. Renal tissue section of DMBA control rats showed tubular degenerative changes and Doxorubicin rats showed glomerulosclerosis, tubular degenerative changes and changes in interstitium of kidney. The combination therapy showed a moderate tubular changes and intact interstitium. However, the treatment with polyherbal formulations showed no abnormality and the architect of kidney tissue appeared intact. Fig 5(a-d)

Fig 5(a-d): Effect of treatment on kidney pathology.

Histopathology of kidney tissue of normal control, DMBA control, Doxorubicin group rats and Polyherbal formulation rats (a) Section of normal rat kidney tissue showing normal appearance. (b) Section of DMBA group rat kidney tissue showing tubular degenerative changes. (c) Section of Doxorubicin group rat kidney tissue glomerulosclerosis, tubular degenerative changes and changes in interstitium of kidney. (d) Section of Polyherbal formulations group rat kidney tissue showing no abnormality and the architect of kidney tissue appeared intact

Effect of drugs on tumor pathology:

The histopathological examination of tumor of DMBA rats showed the fibrocollagenousstroma with cystic spaces and necrosis comprising of degenerated epithelial cells and dense mixed inflammatory cells with metastatic cells. The section of groups treated with Doxorubicin, combination therapy and polyherbal formulations showed absence of metastatic cells and normal epithelial cells along with absence of mixed inflammatory cells. Fig 6(a-d).

Fig 6(a-d): Effect of treatment on tumor pathology.

Histopathology of tumor of DMBA control, Doxorubicin group rats, combination therapy and Polyherbal formulation rats. (a) Section of tumor of DMBA control showing the fibrocollagenous stroma with cystic spaces and necrosis comprising of degenerated epithelial cells and dense mixed inflammatory cells with metastatic cells. (b) Section of tumor of Doxorubicin treated rats showing absence of metastatic cells and absence of dense epithelial cells with cystic spaces. (c) Section of tumor of combination therapy treated rats showing absence of metastatic cells and absence of dense epithelial cells. (d) Section of tumor of polyherbal formulations treated rats showing absence of metastatic cells and loose epithelial cells

DISCUSSION

Chemoprevention by using natural dietary agents has received much attention because of their plausible approach and wide safety.

The present study evaluated the anticancer potential of polyherbal formulations against DMBA induced breast cancer. Doxorubicin is known to possess nephrotoxic effect, so study further evaluated its protective effect with doxorubicin.

DMBA is highly lipophilic and requires metabolic activation for its carcinogenic efficacy. In mammary glands, DMBA is transformed to epoxides, active metabolites which damage the DNA molecule leading for formation of DNA-adducts which leads to initiation of cancer in breast cells. Due to high cell proliferation at this age of sexual maturity, there is an increased metabolic activity leading to higher amount epoxide formation which inturn leads to tumor development in breast cells.^[12, 13]

The first DMBA-induced tumor was observed 6 weeks after administration of carcinogen, after 8 weeks there were tumors in 18 animals and after 12 weeks, tumors were detected in all animals administered with DMBA. These cancerous animals were treated with polyherbal formulations and doxorubicin.

Doxorubicin is one of the most effective chemotherapeutic anthracycline agent which is widely used either alone or in combination with other agents for treatment of breast cancer.

The mechanism of Doxorubicin induced nephrotoxicity is due to free radical generation, disturbance in oxidant-antioxidant systems and iron-dependent oxidative damage of biological macromolecules.^[14]

GSH plays a role in detoxification of xenobiotic compounds and in the antioxidation of reactive oxygen species and free radicals. Low levels of GSH were observed in oxidative stress.^[15] A decrease in the activity of CAT was observed with Doxorubicin^[16].

Reduction in glutathione concentration in kidney indicates the nephrotoxicity of Doxorubicin.^[17] Decrease in the activities of the antioxidant enzymes SOD, CAT and GSH were reported in the DMBA group which are in accordance with the study.^[18]

The above finding correlates with our study where we observed a decrease in CAT, SOD and GSH activity and this effect was greatly reduced in group treated with combinational therapy which is greatly due to antioxidant potential of polyherbal formulations.

There was an increase in biochemical markers like Serum creatinine and blood urea nitrogen observed doxorubicin therapy^[19], which is in accordance with our study where we observed significant increase in Serum creatinine and blood urea nitrogen levels and there was significant decrease in biochemical parameters in combination therapy and groups treated with polyherbal formulations.

There was a significant decrease in body weight observed in DMBA group and treated with Doxorubicin indicative of toxicity of DMBA and Doxorubicin and significant improvement in body weight observed with animals treated with combinational therapy and groups treated with polyherbal formulations.

Tumor volume and tumor weight was greatly reduced in animal treated with Doxorubicin and there was further reduction in tumor weight and tumor volume in rats treated with combination therapy and the effect of polyherbal formulations were comparable with standard drug Doxorubicin.

In this study we observed Polyherbal formulations and doxorubicin synergistically suppressed breast tumor more efficiently than either of these individual agents.

The central finding of the study is that there was more significant regression of tumor volume in polyherbal formulations treated group. The observed effect was due to presence of proanthocyanidines, curcumin, withanolides, andrographolides, piperine, silamarin which have been known for their anticancer activity^[20,21,22,23,24]

The application of Doxorubicin would be greatly enhanced by a combinational therapeutic approach to reduce its toxicity.

CONCLUSION

The present study clearly demonstrates the potent anticancer properties of the polyherbal formulations and synergistic effect along with Doxorubicin. The treatment with polyherbal formulations alone and in combination with Doxorubicin reversed the changes in the biochemical parameters and renal oxidative stress parameters to a normal level, when compared with the control DMBA-induced rat and rats treated with Doxorubicin. The phytochemical revelation of the presence of natural antioxidants such as proanthocyanidines, curcumin, withanolides, andrographolides, piperine, silamarin and flavanoids has further strengthened the evidence for the anticancer property of this polyherbal formulations. Further studies and clinical trials will help evaluate its clinical implications in future research.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to NeocyteHerbtech, Bengaluru for providing Polyherbal formulations and Principal, Al-Ameen College of Pharmacy for the Support.

ABBREVIATION

DMBA : 7,12 Dimethybenze Anthracene

DNA : Deoxy Ribonucleic Acid

CAT : Catalase

GSH : Reduced Glutathione

SOD : Superoxide dismutases

CPCSEA: Committee for the purpose of control and supervision of experiments on animals

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest.

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